

Biamperometric Titration of Ferrous Iron and Cobalt

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A simple method for successive amperometric determination of Fe(II) and Co (II) using two polarised electrodes, has been developed with potassium dichromate as oxidant. Fe (II) is oxidised at an acidity of 2.0 N sulphuric acid at an applied voltage of 50 mv; and Co(II) remains unaffected. After completion of the reaction with iron (II), excess EDTA is added, acidity adjusted to 1.0 N with respect to sulphuric acid, applied voltage is altered to 100 mV and the oxidation is completed with the same titrant.

Biamperometric redox titration has been applied successfully for the estimation of several cations. The use of this technique in mixtures especially under controlled conditions, has been attempted recently in some simple cases¹⁻⁷ in these laboratories. The reproducibility of the titration curves leading to excellent results and the ease of manipulation of experimental technique suggested its use for the present work. It has been now possible to estimate small amounts of Co (II) in presence of iron in a single run of the oxidant. Its suitability is evident especially for metallurgical estimations where various types of steel with large quantities of iron are involved.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

The oxidant used in the present work was potassium dichromate (AnalaR). Cobalt sulphate used was Merck's extra pure and the stock solution was standardised as suggested by Laitinen and Burdett⁸. The solution of divalent iron was prepared from ferrous ammonium sulphate (AnalaR) which was also standardised as a check. The solutions for estimations were obtained by appropriate and accurate dilution of stock solutions with air-free conductivity water. All other chemicals used were of laboratory reagent grade. Linde nitrogen (99.0 percent) was purified⁹, and a slow stream of the purified and dry nitrogen was passed through the mixture prior to, and over the solution during the titration.

Amperometric titrations with two polarised platinum electrodes were carried out

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7. idem., *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1966, **39**.
8. Laitinen, H. A. and Burdett, L. W., *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1268.
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with a circuit similar to that of Foulk and Bawden¹⁰ and Stone and Scholten¹¹. The titration vessel was a 100 ml beaker fitted tightly with rubber stopper provided with necessary holes for the electrodes, nitrogen in-and outlet and burette. The current through the cell was measured by a sensitive galvanometer with two variable resistances, one in series and the other in parallel to allow for the critical damping. Equivalence point was determined graphically from the corresponding plots of galvanometer deflexions *versus* volume of the titrant added.

FIG 1. BIAMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF 2.747 mg Fe(II)
 & 2.980 mg Co(II) PRESENT IN BINARY
 MIXTURE

The acidity of the solution has an important bearing on the experimental results. 20 ml of the titration mixture consisting of ferrous and cobaltous ions together with requisite amount of sulphuric acid, usually adjusted to 2.0 N, was taken in the titration vessel and the titrant (10^{-1} – 10^{-3} N) was added from a semimicroburette with 0.01 ml divisions. The current flowing through the cell, at constant applied potential of the order of 50 millivolts, was measured at regular intervals usually one minute after each addition of the titrant. Under these conditions cobalt (II) remains unaffected. After the completion of the oxidation of iron (II), characterized by a sharp minimum followed by an increase in current, enough EDTA was added to complex Fe (III) and Co (II); the solution was, then, adjusted to 1.0 N with respect to sulphuric acid, the potential was altered to 100 millivolts, and the titration was continued. Experiments were repeated several times and the results of such determinations are given in Table 1.

DISCUSSION

The substances titrated and their reaction products with the titrant are reversible and soluble. Thus, the titration curve, which is in essential agreement with that predict-

10. Foulk, C. W. and Bawden, A. T., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2045.

11. Stone, K. G. and Scholten, H. G., *Anal. Chem.*, 1932, 24, 671.

TABLE I

Determination of Fe (II) and Co (II) present together in solution

Taken	Amount of Fe (II), mg		Taken	Amount of Co (II), mg	
	Found	Difference		Found	Difference
26.80	26.80	0.00	14.15	14.08	-0.07
12.91	12.97	+0.06	5.87	5.85	-0.02
11.18	11.16	-0.02	14.15	14.08	-0.07
8.93	8.97	+0.04	4.71	4.76	+0.05
6.45	6.47	+0.02	2.76	2.79	+0.03
4.91	4.89	-0.02	2.76	2.75	-0.01
2.80	2.80	0.00	1.46	1.46	0.00

ed by Lingane¹², has the shape shown in Fig. 1. The current increases at first with appearance of Fe (III) ion, and passes through maximum, when the fraction titrated is 0.5. The current, then, begins to diminish with addition of more titrant and reaches minimum when iron (II) has been completely oxidised, corresponding the stoichiometric reaction. Cobalt (II) remains unaffected since the normal redox potential of the system $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ is 1.80 volts. Di-sodium salt of EDTA is added in excess at this stage, which complexes the system and lowers the redox potential of cobaltous-cobaltic reversible couple to such a value that divalent cobalt becomes titrable with dichromate in 1.0 N sulphuric acid medium. The current in pre-equivalence region, again, increases in the similar manner, and then falls to minimum. After the equivalence point, water is oxidised at the anode and dichromate is reduced at the cathode; and the limiting current of the latter is observed which increases with the increasing concentration of the titrant. End points are reproducible and the results are good and within experimental error.

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